

**TIL, TA'LIM, TARJIMA
ЯЗЫК, ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ, ПЕРЕВОД
LANGUAGE, EDUCATION, TRANSLATION**

TILSHUNOSLIK

Hakimova Shohista Raimovna

Senior Teacher, Department of the English Language and Literature

Khakimova Farangiz Nadirovna

Student, Faculty of Philology

Gulistan State University

Gulistan City, Uzbekistan

**THE LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL POTENTIAL OF THE REALIAS OF
GREAT BRITAIN IN THE ASPECT OF THE THEORY OF CULTURAL
LITERACY**

ABSTRACT

This article provides an analysis of some socio-political realias of Great Britain in the aspect of the theory of cultural literacy developed by E. D. Hirsch. An analogy is drawn between this theory and the understanding of the term "linguistic and cultural studies" in the most popular studies in this field. The concept of "background knowledge" is analyzed in detail, the structure of this phenomenon is determined and its influence on public discourse is revealed. A semantic analysis of the realias associated with the socio-political life of Great Britain is also carried out. The article proposes a classification of the realias under consideration with examples from linguistic dictionaries and the modern press.

Keywords: linguistic and cultural studies; realia; cultural literacy; vocabulary; background knowledge; structure; discourse.

Hakimova Shohista Raimovna

Katta o'qituvchi, "Ingliz tili va adabiyoti" kafedrasi

Xakimova Farangiz Nadirovna

Talaba, Filologiya fakulteti

Guliston davlat universiteti

**MADANIY SAVODXONLIK NAZARIYASI NUQTAI NAZARIDAN
BUYUK BRITANIYA REALIYALARINING
LINGVOMAMLAKATSHUNOSLIK POTENTIALI**

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada E. D. Xirsh tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan madaniy savodxonlik nazariyasi nuqtai nazaridan Buyuk Britaniyaning ba'zi ijtimoiy-siyosiy realiyalari tahlili keltirilgan. Ushbu nazariya va ushbu sohadagi eng mashhur tadqiqotlarda "lingvomamlakatshunoslik" atamasini tushunish o'rtasida o'xshashlik mavjud. "Fon bilimlari" tushunchasi batafsil tahlil qilindi, ushbu bilimlarning tuzilishi aniqlandi va ularning jamoat nutqiga ta'siri aniqlandi. Shuningdek, Buyuk Britaniyaning ijtimoiy-siyosiy hayoti bilan bog'liq realiyalarning semantik tahlili o'tkazildi. Maqolada ko'rib chiqilayotgan realiyalarning tasnifi lingvistik va mintaqaviy lug'atlar va zamonaviy matbuotdan misollar bilan keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: lingvomamlakatshunoslik; realiya; madaniy savodxonlik; lug'at; fon bilimlari; tuzilishi; nutqi.

Хакимова Шохиста Раимовна

Старший преподаватель, кафедра английского языка и литературы

Хакимова Фарангиз Надыровна

Студентка, филологический факультет

Гулистанский государственный университет

г. Гулистан, Узбекистан

**ЛИНГВОСТРАНОВЕДЧЕСКИЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ РЕАЛИЙ
ВЕЛИКОБРИТАНИИ В АСПЕКТЕ ТЕОРИИ КУЛЬТУРНОЙ
ГРАМОТНОСТИ**

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье приводится анализ некоторых общественно-политических реалий Великобритании в аспекте теории культурной грамотности, разработанной Э. Д. Хиршем. Проводится аналогия между данной теорией и пониманием термина «лингвострановедение» в наиболее популярных исследованиях в данной области. Детально проанализировано понятие «фоновые знания», определена структура этих знаний и выявлено их влияние на общественный дискурс. Также проведен семантический анализ реалий, связанных с общественно-политической жизнью Великобритании. В статье предлагается классификация рассматриваемых реалий с примерами из лингвострановедческих словарей и современной прессы.

Ключевые слова: лингвострановедение; реалия; культурная грамотность; словарь; фоновые знания; структура; дискурс.

Introduction. The concept of cultural literacy, which later formed the basis of the "The New Dictionary of Cultural Literacy", was developed by E. D. Hirsch. The emergence of this concept was a response to the social demand that faced American society in the 80s of the 20th century. According to many figures in the field of education, the literacy rate of the nation began to decline since the 60s of the 20th century. Moreover, this process affected not only children with developmental delays, but also students of higher educational institutions. The decline of political activity, the growth of ignorance and illiteracy of young people led to the identification of the problem of background knowledge. It is generally recognized that this decline occurred at a time when the need for truly functional literacy began to be felt by many as a guarantee of economic well-being and even as a condition for maintaining the social structure of society. Before publishing the dictionary, E. D. Hirsch published a monograph entitled "Cultural Literacy. What Every American Needs to Know", where he outlined the main postulates of his theory. In it, he noted that modern complex enterprises depend on the cooperation of people of different specialties. Where communication weakens, the same happens with enterprises; young middle-level employees who are not educated enough to easily understand each other repeat the story of Babel and spend a lot of time explaining what their grandfathers could express with one succinct analogy. As for the socio-political life of the nation, the lack of education of a citizen actually deprives him of the right to vote. Semi-literate people are doomed not only to poverty, but also to misunderstanding controversial issues, speeches of politicians, newspaper articles and, feeling themselves victims of oversimplification, do not trust the system in which they are supposedly the masters [1, 3].

The Problem of Research and Novelty. The novelty of this study lies in the theory put forward that there is some dependence of true literacy on the knowledge of special information shared by all members of the community. This information is nothing but background knowledge in the terminology of E. M. Kostomarov and V. G. Vereshchagin. E. D. Hirsch pays serious attention to the formation, properties and psychological structure of background knowledge. They are formed in intra-national communication. This process is based on the formation and existence of the national language as the main tool of communication and national culture, the creation of linguistic and cultural dictionaries [3, 54]. A unified national literary language develops during the formation of national economic and social ties and is supported by the education system. E. D. Hirsch devotes an entire chapter of the book to the history of the formation of principles, values and traditions of American society, which turns out to be closely related to the process of creating national myths (names, events, legends) and symbols — "civil religion". National culture includes a "civil religion" [4, 20], but is based on a much more diverse vocabulary, suitable for expressing different, even opposing points of view. Cultural vocabulary,

especially in the part of "civil religion", is fixed in textbooks, books for reading. The author emphasizes that the linguistic and cultural dictionaries [5, 31] of society arise as a result of the mutual influence and interpenetration of all groups and strata of the population, and this process is most active in the giant cauldron of large cities. As a result of historical development, different peoples have developed different dictionaries, but they are all quite broad, have branched roots and make this culture viable [1, 77]. Reading and writing are not only acts of decoding and encoding information, but also acts of communication, which requires possession of some generally recognized knowledge-concepts that are not literally registered on this page.

Cultural Literacy and Background Knowledge. Cultural literacy, unlike expert knowledge, is shared by all members of the community. This is the mobile piece of information that the community found useful and, therefore, worthy of preservation. Only a small part of what is read or heard occupies a safe place on the shelves of the memory of a culturally literate person, but the importance of this stored information is beyond doubt.

Background knowledge is the basis of public discourse. They allow you to understand daily newspapers and television news, speeches of political leaders and even jokes. This knowledge is changing very slowly. Approximately 80% of commonly used information has remained unchanged for more than 100 years. Such cultural conservatism is useful for social communication: it allows people of different generations, political orientations, national and religious affiliation, and different regions of the country to communicate.

The psychological structure of background knowledge is a multilevel semantic scheme, at different depths of which information lies, different in frequency of use and, therefore, in ease of actualization. A person, as a rule, tends to interpret his impressions in average categories: not too specific and not too generalized. The basic classifications themselves, in terms of which a person understands the world, are presented to him through commonly occurring examples.

In the book by E. D. Hirsch, an original experiment is described in detail, as a result of which it was found that a typical bird for an Englishman is a creature like a robin and it is its designation, unlike the name of a chicken or an ostrich, that easily fits into phrases composed using the name of the "bird" class. It also turned out that the basic information about the class is further from the surface when it is extracted from memory than specific information about a familiar form, which is more often used in everyday life. That is why, for a successful mutual understanding, it is often enough, instead of a detailed and in-depth knowledge of theories, facts and books, a superficial awareness of them. The vocabulary of words and idioms of an educated person is about 50 thousand units. The full text of long-term memory contains a much larger amount of knowledge, but the basic dictionary serves as a simple and easily accessible index for them. When expressing their thoughts, a person should not only extract their own schemes, but also keep in mind how much they are shared by communication partners. It has been experimentally shown that children switch

to egocentric speech, describing something little-known to them. Both children and adults, culturally illiterate people, lack, in addition to just information, also easily accessible information about what others know and about the system of their associations. The same is necessary for specialists so that they can communicate their knowledge using publicly available analogies [1, 134].

The Role of Background Knowledge in Understanding Realias. To identify this type of knowledge, E. D. Hirsch has developed a number of rules.

1) Firstly, most of the information is either above or below the level of cultural literacy. A significant part of the information is so specific that it is known only to experts, and, therefore, is located above the level of general knowledge. At the same time, some of the information, such as, for example, the names of flowers, animals, etc., is basic and well-known and is not included in the dictionary of cultural literacy. By definition, the vocabulary of cultural literacy is between specialized and general.

2) Secondly, it should be established how widely this concept is known in American culture. Only those concepts that the majority of educated Americans are aware of can be attributed to the dictionary of cultural literacy. When selecting such concepts, E. D. Hirsch relied on the frequency of their use in national periodicals. From his point of view, if a periodical refers to an event, a person or an object without defining them, then it can be assumed that most readers are familiar with them. Apparently, this event, person, object are part of the general knowledge and, therefore, part of the cultural literacy of the nation.

3) Thirdly, it must be remembered that cultural literacy is not knowledge of current events, although it can be used to understand these events more deeply. To become a component of cultural literacy, some information must have a stable significance. Such information has already found a certain place in the collective memory or has prospects of finding it. This is what contributes to the stability of cultural literacy in America. According to E. D. Hirsch, it is often difficult to determine the stable significance, since in the age of communication, the lifetime of many concepts in collective memory is quite short. What seems monumental today often becomes trivial tomorrow. These are the criteria for selecting culturally-marked lexical units that relate to the field of cultural literacy [2, 11].

Practical Analysis. The main purpose of linguistics is to provide a non-native speaker with background knowledge, in volume, form and content approaching the background knowledge of a native speaker of a given language and culture. Linguistics sets itself the task of researching linguistic units that most vividly reflect the national peculiarities of the culture of the native-speaking people and the environment of their existence. These units include:

- 1) realias;
- 2) connotative vocabulary – words that coincide in their main meaning, but differ in cultural and historical associations;

3) background vocabulary – words that denote objects and phenomena that have analogues in the comparable culture, but differ in some national peculiarities of functioning, form, purpose of objects.

One of the components of the linguistic and cultural aspect is represented by realias, which are understood as objects or phenomena of material culture, ethnic and national characteristics, customs, rituals and traditions, as well as historical facts or processes that often do not have lexical equivalents in other languages. It is the realias that make up the national heritage and the history of a country. Studying the realias of a particular language allows you to understand the mentality of native speakers of a foreign language. The emergence of new realias in the life of society contributes to the emergence of new realias in the language, and the time for this can be quite clearly tracked, since the vocabulary reacts very sensitively to all changes taking place in society. In reality, the closeness between languages and culture is clearly manifested, they have a corresponding national flavor.

The focus of this article falls on one of the thematic groups of realias traditionally distinguished in linguistic research – socio-political realias. Socio-political realias form part of the socio-political vocabulary, reflecting country-specific phenomena and concepts from the sphere of socio-political life. These realias should be considered in inseparable connection with the historical and political events and phenomena of a certain country. Since no detailed analysis of the realias related to the socio-political life of Great Britain has been carried out before, it seems appropriate to present their classification here, accompanied by examples from linguistic dictionaries and the modern press.

1. State symbols: “Union Jack” – the national British flag. Full name “Union Jack or Union Flag Royal”;

“Dieu et mon droit” (“God and my right” – “Бог и мое право”) – the motto of the English (from 18th century – British) monarchy from the times of Henrik V (1413–1422);

“Royal coat of arms of the United Kingdom” – the official coat of arms of the British monarch [6, 37].

2. Authorities.

- The realias associated with the queen.

“Imperial State Crown” – crown of the British Empire;

“Great Seal of the Realm” – The Great Seal of the Kingdom;

“The Crown Jewels of the United Kingdom” – There are 142 royal ceremonial items.

- The realias of legislative power (authorities and bearers of power).

“House of Lords” – the upper house of the UK Parliament;

“House of Commons” – the lower house of the UK Parliament;

“Speaker” – Chairman of the lower House of Commons;

“Lord High Chancellor” – the highest dignitary of the state, appointed by the Sovereign on the proposal of the Prime Minister for five years;

“Chief Whips” – parliamentary organizers, managing parties;

“Black rod” – «Черный жезл», Heraldmaster (House of Lords);

“yeomanusher” – assistant Heraldmaster;

“Royal Assent” – Royal sanction is the method by which the monarch formally approves an act of the legislature [8, 44].

3. Political parties.

“Tories” – “тори”, English political party; originated in the late 70s – early 80s of the 17th century;

“whigs” – “виги”, the historical name of the Liberal Party of Great Britain.

4. Classes, class castes.

Classism is an important element of English socio-political life, which is undergoing changes over time. In this group of realias there are many historicisms that are associated with the names of classes in different periods of the existence of England. Thus, the history of the X–XI centuries is represented by the following realias: “earl” – “граф” (титул высшей аристократии англосаксонской Британии в XI в., возникший под влиянием датского завоевания Англии); “churl” / “ceorl” – “керлы”, commoners (a layer of simple free farmers-peasants in the Anglo-Saxon period of British history), “geneats” – “гениты”, “geburs” – “гебуры”; “kotsetlas” – котселты [9, 17].

In the period from the 15th to the 17th century, English society is represented by the following classes of people: “cottagers and labourers”; “husbandman” (or other tradesmen) – “купец” or “фермер”, “yeoman” – “йомен”, “мелкий фермер”.

The class structure has changed significantly recently. In 2017, a large study of the classes of Great Britain (so-called “Great British Class Survey”) was conducted, which revealed the existence of 7 classes in the country. The names of the classes have not yet been translated into Russian, and therefore the author's translation is proposed in the article:

“precariat” – «прекариат», also called the unstable proletariat. The poorest and most deprived class in Britain;

“traditional working class” – “традиционный рабочий класс”;

“emergent service workers” – “развивающийся класс работников сфер услуг”;

“technical middle class” – “технический средний класс или технари”;

“new affluent workers” – “обеспеченные наемные работники”;

“established middle class” – “устоявшийся средний класс”;

“elite” – “элита” [11, 57].

5. Titles and titles.

“Peer of realm” – “пэр Соединенного Королевства”;

“life peers” – “пожизненный пэр”;

“hereditary peer” – “наследственный пэр”;

“representative peer” – “представительный пэр”, elected by members of the House of Peers of Scotland and the House of Peers of Ireland to participate in the British House of Lords [11, 58].

6. Socio-political movements.

“lollards” – “лолларды”; the most democratically minded followers of the religious reformer J. Wycliffe;

“puritans” – “пуритане”; the movement of the 16th-17th centuries for the purification of the Anglican Church from the remnants of Catholicism in worship, rituals and doctrine, distinguished by the strictness of morals and religious intolerance;

“levellers” – “уравнители”; radical political party during the English Revolution, before 1647 left wing independents;

“diggers” – “землекопы”, “диггеры”; the extreme left wing of revolutionary democracy during the English Revolution;

“luddites” – “луддиты”; workers, participants of the first demonstrations (late 18th – early 19th centuries, England) against the consequences of the industrial revolution, which was expressed in the destruction of machine tools and factory equipment;

“anti-Corn Law League” – the organization of British industrialists and economists, which advocated the abolition of the Grain Laws, defended the interests of the industrial bourgeoisie [11, 59].

Recently, the group of "socio-political movements" has been enriched by lexical units related to Brexit, which is understood as the process of Britain's withdrawal from the European Union. At the moment, Brexit dictionaries are being created, where neologisms related to this political phenomenon are recorded in one way or another. Here are some examples of the realias that have emerged over the past four years, since the national referendum was held:

“hard Brexit” – «жесткий» Брекзит – the option of the UK leaving the EU with a complete rejection of access to the single market and access to the customs union;

“soft Brexit” – «мягкий» Брекзит – the option of the UK's exit from the EU, which would allow the UK and Europe to keep relations as close as possible to the existing agreements;

“white Brexit” – «белый» Брекзит – a bracket option in which Britons can remain members of the EU customs union;

“brexodus” – a situation in which the number of Europeans who came to the UK is greater than those who left the country;

“clean Brexit” – the option of the UK leaving the EU without a withdrawal agreement;

“cliff edge” – the option of a "hard" Brexit: a break without follow-up and consequences;

“green Brexit” – «зеленый» Брекзит – a term indicating that the UK Government planned to establish an independent monitoring body for compliance with environmental standards after the country's withdrawal from the European Union;

“remainers” – people defending the position that the UK should not leave the EU;

“leavers” – people supporting the tarpaulin [12, 62-63].

The analysis of the realias reflecting the socio-political features of the UK shows that this subject group has been significantly expanded due to serious socio-political changes. It should be noted that consideration of new socio-political realias in foreign language lessons gives the educational process authenticity and relevance.

Results of the Study. Thus, cultural literacy is a set of background knowledge that an American should be familiar with in order to adequately understand the meaning of a statement. E. D. Hirsch sees the influence of background knowledge on the understanding of the text in phenomena similar to the following. The beginning of a school textbook on chemistry is given: "You start studying chemistry at a time when more and more people are concerned about the declining quality of life. Chemistry can help you gain a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the environment in which you live now. If you are curious and want to know more about natural processes, minerals, water and solutions, atmospheric gases, studying chemistry will captivate you." So, it is assumed that even before reading this passage, the child should know what the words "chemistry", "solution", "declining quality of life" mean. But even just looking at each word in the last phrase, you can see what a huge stock of background knowledge is behind them. To understand this phrase quickly and accurately, you need more than knowledge of the meanings of individual words or the ability to draw logical conclusions. It is necessary to know the background information that the author has, in this case, the widely discussed problem of pollution of rivers, atmosphere, etc. Neither the word nor the concept of "pollution" is mentioned in the passage. To understand it, you need to know not only that rivers and air are polluted, but also that this pollution is somehow connected with the words "declining quality of life". Having no background knowledge, a person with a good knowledge of English and with good reading skills will be puzzled by comparing the concept of "quality of life" with reference to aqueous solutions [2, 14].

The ability to read and understand what is read depends not only on broad knowledge, but also knowledge that can be called mutual. Communication between the reader and the writer is always associated with the ability to see the subtext that remains unspoken literally, but which should be felt by both the reader and the writer if communication proceeds effectively. Since successful learning through reading is conditioned by the effectiveness of the communicative operation, E. D. Hirsch came to the conclusion that both reading and learning are powerfully influenced by how fully background knowledge is shared by writer and reader, teacher and student. To study well, you need to know a lot, as well as have the special knowledge that allows you to read between the lines. Therefore, learning depends on communication, effective communication depends on background knowledge. The best way to fulfill this requirement is to ensure that both the trainees and the trainees actually have a universal amount of special knowledge. The main idea of the theory of E. D. Hirsch's

idea is that the effectiveness of solving related problems of learning and literacy depends on the presence of mutual background knowledge on both sides of learning, which E. D. Hirsch called cultural literacy. He notes that the content of this knowledge is not a secret, it can be systematically transmitted to students. Further, the scientist states that if it is possible to transfer such knowledge, it will be possible to achieve universal literacy, which is necessary to lay the foundation for further educational, economic and social transformations.

As an example, the history of the development of education in France (a country with a multicultural population), where its high level has been achieved, is given. Up to the 18th century, at least four languages were spoken here. The French school system, according to Yu. Weber, turned illiterate peasants into Frenchmen, it was the school system, not the peasant house, that performed this miracle.

One of the main reasons for the decline in the level of education in the United States, E. D. Hirsch calls the use of so-called practice-oriented, relevant materials at the primary and secondary levels of secondary schools. The subsequent disappearance of traditional history, mythology, and literature from school curricula had far-reaching and disastrous consequences for national culture. According to recent studies, there is a high correlation between skills and specific knowledge, and this correlation persists at all levels. In addition, the conservatism inherent in literacy is noted, for example, spelling rules. Similar conservatism is also characteristic of other aspects of cultural literacy. It is useful for the purposes of national communication, helps grandchildren communicate with their grandfathers, Southerners with residents of other states, whites with blacks, Asians with Latin Americans, Republicans with Democrats. Therefore, a good definition of cultural literacy would be the ability to communicate effectively with strangers. Teaching people from the lower strata of society the basics of traditional culture can help them rise economically, they will be able to communicate effectively outside the narrow social sphere. Thus, conservatism inherent in cultural literacy inevitably leads to the following paradox: the social goals of liberalism require educational conservatism. From the point of view of E. D. Hirsch, social and economic progress can be achieved by teaching everyone to read and communicate.

From the moment of its appearance, the concept of cultural literacy instantly aroused interest and continues to attract the attention of scientists in different countries. O. A. Kornilov noted that the value of the study lies in the fact that E. D. Hirsch was able to highlight the politics, public institutions, and customs of the United States from the position of national culture. It is this sphere of the dictionary of cultural literacy that is most important for a full command of the language as a means of communication, since it reflects interpersonal, local, national, class differences, which is undoubtedly an immense sphere to describe [7, 72].

The idea of raising the cultural level of young people and expanding their horizons by adding a number of general education topics from the field of literature, geography, history, cultural studies to the curricula is extremely relevant, interesting

and deserves worthy attention. Moreover, such an idea and the version of its implementation proposed by E. D. Hirsch have no analogues of their kind.

Discussion of the Results. The concept of cultural literacy was an interesting material for discussions. Its application in practice caused a flurry of criticism. Many scientists, for example, P. V. Sysoev [10, 267]), do not agree with the method of selecting culturally marked lexical units of the dictionary of cultural literacy. The selection of words, as explained by E. D. Hirsch, was carried out by him and his six colleagues through a detailed discussion of each proposed concept. Many scientists consider this technique invalid. The cultural literacy test developed by E. Hirsch and his colleagues, consists of multiple choice questions, which often does not reflect the actual knowledge of the subject, but only demonstrates some kind of training in the field under test. Since cultural literacy affects the mastery of writing and reading skills, according to the researcher, it should be taught already in elementary school, selecting educational texts saturated with vocabulary information. The author's position that unconditional preference should be given to these texts rather than artistic ones seems controversial: it is hardly worth depriving children of the opportunity to join the beauty and fascination of works reflecting the world of human feelings and the richness of life situations.

Conclusion. Based on the conducted research, we believe that the finiteness of the list of information necessary for cultural literacy will force people to learn several hundred pages of linguistic and cultural content standing between ignorance and education, however, there is a danger that many will find it possible to limit themselves to this list, allowing for a superficial knowledge of most of the topics. Such an approach would lead to the impoverishment of the "full text of long-term memory" and – subsequently - a catastrophic narrowing of the dictionary of cultural literacy itself. Despite the doubts and objections that arise about the theory of E. D. Hirsch, we believe that the ideas of cultural literacy of members of society developed by him as a condition for effective public communication, interdependence in the development of knowledge and skills, the study of the psychological structure of background linguistic and cultural knowledge are undoubtedly interesting.

Иқтибослар/Сноски/References

1. Hirsch, E. D. Cultural Literacy. What Every American Needs to Know. – New York: Random House, 1988. – 253 p.
2. Hirsch, E. D., Kett, J. F., Trefil, J. The New Dictionary of Cultural Literacy. What Every American Needs to Know. – Boston & New York: Houghton Muffin Company, 2002. – 254 p.
3. Krause, W. D. The foreign and the text: foreign language communication and its results. Potsdam: Potsdam University Publishing House, 2010. – 303 p.
4. Девкин, В. Д. Вопросы лингвострановедения и лексикологии. – Москва: Прометей, 2003. – 120 с. (Devkin, V. D. Voprosy lingvostranovedeniya i leksikologii. – Moskva: Prometej, 2003. – 120 s.).

5. Карпова, О. М. Лексикографические портреты словарей современного английского языка. – Иваново: ИГПУ, 2004. – 88 с. (Karpova, O. M. Leksikograficheskie portrety slovarej sovremennogo anglijskogo yazyka. – Ivanovo: IGPU, 2004. – 88 s.).

6. Конецкая, В. П. Лексико-семантические характеристики языковых реалий. Приложение к лингвострановедческому словарю «Великобритания». – Москва: 1980. – 78 с. (Koneckaya, V. P. Leksiko-semanticheskie harakteristiki yazykovykh realij. Prilozhenie k lingvostranovedcheskomu slovaryu «Velikobritaniya». – Moskva: 1980. – 78 s.).

7. Корнилов, О. А. Языковые картины мира как производные национальных менталитетов. Третье издание. – Москва: КДУ, 2011. – 94 с. (Kornilov, O. A. Yazykovye kartiny mira kak proizvodnye nacional'nyh mentalitetov. Tret'e izdanie. – Moskva: KDU, 2011. – 94 s.).

8. Павлоцкий, В. М. Знакомимся с Британией. – Санкт-Петербург: Кристалл, 2002. – 105 с. (Pavlockij, V. M. Znakomimsya s Britaniej. – Sankt-Peterburg: Kristall, 2002. – 105 s.).

9. Паксман, Дж. Англия: портрет народа. – Санкт-Петербург: Амфора, 2010. – 70 с. (Paksman, Dzh. Angliya: portret naroda. – Sankt-Peterburg: Amfora, 2010. – 70 s.).

10. Сысоев, П. В. Концепция языкового поликультурного образования (на материале культуроведения США). – Москва: Еврошкола, 2003. – 406 с. (Sysoev, P. V. Konsepciya yazykovogo polikul'turnogo obrazovaniya (na materiale kul'turovedeniya SShA). – Moskva: Evroshkola, 2003. – 406 s.).

11. Тер-Минасова, С. Г. Язык и межкультурная коммуникация. – Москва: МГУ, 2004. – 397 с. (Ter-Minasova, S. G. Yazyk i mezhkul'turnaya kommunikaciya. – Moskva: MGU, 2004. – 397 s.).

12. Томахин, Г. Д. Страны Соединенного Королевства: лингвострановедческий справочник. Второе издание. – Москва: Просвещение, 2001. – 184 с. (Tomahin, G. D. Strany Soedinennogo Korolevstva: lingvostranovedcheskij spravochnik. Vtoroe izdanie. – Moskva: Prosveshchenie, 2001. – 184 s.).